

Green Recruitment Management Practice and Performance of Food and Beverage Manufacturing Firms in Rivers State

Okoroafor, Onyinyechi Gloria¹, Prof Chris C. Orga², Mbah, Paulinus Chigozie³

¹Department of Human Resource Management, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu Nigeria

²³Department of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu Nigeria

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The study evaluated green recruitment management practices and the Performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers State. The specific objectives were to: examine the relationship between the online application of candidates and output; ascertain the relationship between Video-based interviews of the applicants and quality service of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers State. The study employed a descriptive survey design. The area of this study was River State, Nigeria. The populations of the study were five (5) selected food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers State, with Nine hundred and sixty one (961) selected staff from the firms. To determine the adequate sample size of 274, the study used Freund and William's statistic formula. A total of 226 staff returned the questionnaire accurately filled. Data from the questionnaire were analyzed with the aid of SPSS version 23 using simple, percentages and correlation coefficient. The findings indicated that Online application of candidates had significant positive relationship with the output $r(95, n=226), = .517 < .850, p < .05$) and Video-based interview of the applicants had significant positive relationship with the quality service of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state as reported in the probability value of $r(95, n=226), = .402 < .790, p < .05$). The study concluded that online application of candidates and Video-based interview of the applicants had significant positive relationship with the output and the reduced expenses of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers State. The study recommended among others that the management of food and beverage manufacturing firms should endeavour to have effective online application to select best talents to the success of organizational goals and objectives.

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ABSTRACT

Keywords: Green Recruitment Management Practice; Performance; Beverage Manufacturing Firms

Background

As the world's population grows, so will pollution from industrial activities. As a result, governments, stakeholders, customers, employees, and competitors are putting pressure on businesses to adopt environmentally friendly practices in the long run. These practices can assist firms in improving their long-term performance and gaining a competitive advantage. Environmental degradation and climate change have emerged as two of the most pressing issues of the twenty-first century, resulting in economic losses caused by weather and climate-related disasters such as devastating hurricanes, droughts, heat waves, and wildfires. Human activities are thought to have already caused 1.08 degrees Celsius of global warming above pre-industrial levels (United Nations Environment Programme, 2019). The business sector has frequently been at the center of all sustainability discussions, and it is widely regarded as a major source of environmental harm at the local, regional, and global levels (Moscardo, et al., 2013).

Green recruitment management practices have been viewed as an important component in GHRM practices. Candidates' green awareness is the basic aspect of Green Recruitment, and involves personality factors that enable organizational environmental goals to be achieved, such as green consciousness, conscientiousness, and the agreeableness of candidates (Katima, 2017). The profile of a fresh job aspirant ready to enter the job market is changing. Apart from being young, enthusiastic, eager to grab opportunities, confident, friendly, they have a high sense of awareness of the most serious and current issues, political, social and environmental. Green recruitment refers to the procedure of hiring people having behaviour, knowledge and skills of environment management systems in the organization (Obaid & Alias, 2015). In green recruitment and selection applications are invited through online mediums like e-mail, online application forms or the global talent pool. If possible, telephone or video-based interviews are conducted to minimize any travel-related environmental impact (Saini & Shukla, 2016). Since recruitment deals with attracting prospective candidates to apply for available job vacancies in organizations either internally or externally, this can be used as a platform to attract employees who not only have skills and knowledge on environmental conservation but also have an interest to conserve the environment. Recruiting candidates with green bend of mind makes it easy for firms to induct professionals who are aware of sustainable processes and are already familiar with basics like recycling, conservation, and creating a more logical world (Sanyal, 2017). Based on this, the study aimed at evaluating green recruitment management practices and Performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The focus of current companies is green human resource management, where human resource department is engaging in greening the culture of the organizations by maintaining green offices and green practices. The priority of every firm or industry is to growth, ensure increase sales volume, profit, and enhance their technological utilization and improve on employment generation. Attainment to a great height by firms relies much on the environmental factors. Environment remains the major offer in line with some degree of influence like turbulence, placid hostility and benevolence to firms. Coordination with the business environment is the condition for the success of the firm's management.

In order to achieve organizational environmental goals of going green, green HRM is very vital factor. As a result of poor management there is lack of e- mail applications of the employees, poor online application of candidates, and lack of global talent pool, low Video-based interview of the applicants and online interview. This can be achieved by hiring and maintaining green employees, having sufficient knowledge and skills of green employees.

Consequently, most firms are now closing down or folding up based on this situation resulting to low unit of output, cost and waste increase, turnover, and low communication rate. The study therefore was carried out to evaluate green recruitment management practices and Performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the green recruitment management practices and Performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers State. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the relationship between online application of candidates and units of output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers State.
- ii. Ascertain the relationship between Video-based interview of the applicants and quality service of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers State

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- i. What is the relationship between online application of candidates and output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers State?
- ii. What is the relationship between Video-based interview of the applicants and quality service of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers State?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following Hypotheses guided the study

- i. Online application of candidates has relationship with the output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers State.
- ii. Video-based interview of the applicants have relationship with the quality service of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers State.

Scope of the Study

The study sought to evaluate green recruitment management practices and Performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state, Nigeria. Apparently, the geographical scope of the study is in the south eastern part of Nigeria. The study covered the following dependent and independent variables: e-mail applications of the employees and output; Video-based interview of the applicants and reduced expenses of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state, Nigeria.

Conceptual Review

Green

Going green simply implies the process of conserving the mother earth's natural resources as well as preserving and supporting individual resources. This indicates that, HRM policies are used to promote and support the sustainable use of resources and preserve the natural environment. (Marhatta and Saragil, 2013). The concept of going green in organization means to pursue knowledge and practices that can lead to more environmentally friendly and ecologically responsible decisions and lifestyles, which can help protect the environment and sustain its natural resources for current and future generations (Middletown Thrall Library, 2019).

Recruitment

Recruitment is the process of finding and hiring the best and most qualified candidate for a job opening, in a timely and cost-effective manner. It can also be defined as the process of searching for prospective employees and stimulating and encouraging them to apply for jobs in an organization. Obviously, the main reason why the recruitment process is implemented is to find the persons who are best qualified for the positions within the company, and who will help them towards attaining organizational goals (Martin, 2016).

Management

Management can be referred to as the process of planning, organizing, staffing, directing, coordinating, and controlling, at other times it is used to describe people as the task of managing them. It is also known as the body of knowledge, practice, and discipline. Management is an art of getting things done through those people who can be

manager or non-manager. At the level of the chief executive, the work is done through the functional managers, things at the middle level are implemented through the supervisors and at the lower level of the management through the workers (Kumar, 2019). Management involves conceiving, initiating and bringing together the various elements; coordinating, actuating, integrating the diverse organizational components while sustaining the viability of the organization towards some pre-determined goals (Prachi, 2021; Ile, Otti, & Mbah, 2022).

Green Recruitment Management Practice

Green Recruitment is the process of recruiting new talent who is aware of an ongoing process, environmental systems and familiar with environmental conservation. Green assured the recruitment of new talent who is familiar with the practice green and environmental systems that will support effective environmental management in organizations (Wiernik, Stephan and Deniz, 2016). In a competition most of the employees who are creative and innovative will increase the organization for recruiting, hiring quality staff, is a challenge that is very important in the war of talent and even companies also know the fact that being an entrepreneur is an effective way to attract new talent (Renwick, Redman and Maguire, 2013). Prachi (2011) state that green toughest of recruits is a free recruitment process to minimize the environmental impact of paper. Recruitment is usually done through online media such as websites, email, online application forms and other applications.

Components of Green Recruitment Management Practice that Formed Part of the Objectives of the Study

Online Application of Candidates

Online recruitment (which also known as internet recruiting or e-recruitment) gives room for businesses to use varieties of internet-based solutions – these include: job listings, online advertising, social media and organizations websites to source and hire the best employees. The consistent use of internet for hiring has made it faster to source employees and conduct interviews as well as process the vital paperwork needed to recruit and train employees. Online recruitment provides businesses with proper and economical way to fill positions, (Fountain, 2023). The Use of cloud based or internet-based software, jobs can be posted, accept applications and communicate with applicants and monitor their progress throughout the whole recruitment process (Thomas, 2023).

Video-based Interview

A video interview is an organized proceeding that takes place on video calling software or specialized video interviewing software where a candidate is asked questions designed to discover whether or not they should be hired to do a specific job (Totaljobs, 2021). The experience of a video conference interview is notably different from that of a one-way video interview. Videoconferencing as a communication technology allows for a real-time, online synchronous conversation to occur, with the ability to send and receive audiovisual information compared with other online methods for qualitative data collection (i.e., email interviews, online forums, and instant messaging), videoconferencing more closely resembles the in-person qualitative interview (Tuttas, 2015). A video interview is a job interview that takes place remotely and uses video technology as the communication medium. Video interviews are a popular tool for talent acquisition because they can save an organization time and money compared to traditional, in-person or face-to-face interviews.

Performance

Green performance management consists of issues related to environmental concerns and policies of the company. It also concentrates on use of environmental responsibilities (Epstein and Roy, 1997). GHRM incorporates many traditional practices (i.e., employee engagement, recruitment, rewards, and training) to improve an organization's environmental performance. Such environmental/green human resource processes improve efficiency and decrease costs. Performance tests the way available functional inputs can be leveraged by an economic system or enterprise to produce useful outputs. This idea pushes economies towards higher degrees of production efficiency and therefore higher economic growth and living standards. As a consequence, improving efficiency is a crucial goal for communities to increase their relative income (Kyra, 2017; Edeh, Nnamani & Mbah, 2023).

Components of Performance that Formed Part of the Objectives of the Study

Output

Outputs often apply to the number of visited customers during a given duration. The organization needs to become accustomed if there is a decline in the output of the organization due to alteration in the external or internal environment (Kotler, 2018). Output is a quantity of goods or services produced in a specific time period (for instance, a year). For a business producing one good, output could simply be the number of units of that good produced in each time period, such as a month or a year. Output refers to the total production of goods and services of a whole country over a given period – its gross domestic product. The term may refer to all the work, energy, goods, or services produced by an individual, company, factory or machine (David, 2017; Eze, Mbah & Oboko, 2022).

Quality Service

Quality Service is a measure of how products and services supplied by a company meet and surpass consumer expectations. Companies often introduce new products to maintain competitiveness. However, it is the service quality and the resulting customer satisfaction that are decisive for long-term business success. Service quality management encompasses a variety of procedures to assess the quality of services according to customer expectations. It also includes the maintenance and long-term monitoring of all services offered to customers, to track developments in quality and measure the efficiency of improvement efforts. By measuring the size of the gap between expectations and reality, companies are delivered with actionable insights for targeted improvements. Moreover, companies profit from the additional benefit of getting to know their target audiences much better along the way. Continuous service quality management enables companies to identify and reduce sources of errors and customer complaints (Melaku, 2015; Nnamani, Ugwu, & Oluka, 2023).

Conceptual Framework of the Study

Figure 1

Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by The Resource Based View (RBV) theory by Edith Penrose

The theory was derived from the idea of economist Edith Penrose. The theory argues that resources including employees, systems and business partners are combined into ways of working which are rare, inimitable, valuable and non-replaceable so that they become sources of competitive advantage (Tyson & York, 2006). The resource-based view (RBV) is a managerial framework used to determine the strategic resources a firm can exploit to achieve sustainable competitive advantage (Barney, 1991). RBV focuses attention on an organization's internal resources as a means of organizing processes and obtaining a competitive advantage. This theory is relevant and anchored to the study because to get human resources who are rare, inimitable, valuable, green and unique, the organization must ensure that their recruitment and selection practice guarantee hiring of people with the right skills which they also must understand that for the employees to be a source of competitive advantage, they need to be knowledgeable. Knowledge acquired and possessed by employees is a source of competitive advantage as this is tacit knowledge which is impossible to imitate.

Empirical Review

The Relationship Between Online Application of Candidates and Output

Sarinah, Rahmat and Asep (2016) conducted a study on The Effect of Recruitment and Employee Selection on Employee Placement and Its Impacts towards Employee Performance. The purpose of the study was to determine the effect of the implementation of the recruitment and placement of employee selection and its impact on the performance of employees of PT Sriwijaya Air Jakarta Indonesian. The study adopted the path analysis method. The finding showed that recruitment and selection influence significantly the placement of employees. The study concluded that Human resources that are reliable and competent are a major factor in the competitive advantage PT Sriwijaya Air.

Chukwuka and Eboh (2018) conducted an empirical investigation of the effect of green business practices on the organizational performance of selected manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The specific objective of this study was to determine the extent to which green business practices affect the manufacturing firm's productivity in Nigeria. This study adopted the survey design. A simple random sampling technique was used in selecting the 10 manufacturing firms in Nigeria. A sample size of 543 respondents was determined from the population of 5705 drawn from management, middle and lower cadre of the selected manufacturing firms using Cochran (1977) statistical formula. A stratified sampling technique was also used to determine the proportional allocation of questionnaire to management cadre, middle cadre and lower cadre. Designed questionnaire and personal interview were used for primary data collection. The questionnaire was structured on 5-point Likert scale. The validity of the instrument was ascertained using content validity. Data were analyzed and the hypotheses were tested using linear regression analysis. Probability level of significance was given at 5%. Data were presented using simple percentages. Findings revealed that green business initiatives had significant and positive effect on the selected manufacturing firm's productivity ($r=.756$, $F=346.024$; $T=18.602$; $p=.000$). In conclusion, the implementation of green business practices, principles and processes will lead to very positive outcome that will be visibly manifested in the organization and the environment.

Malik, et al. (2020) investigated the impact of GHRM practices and green intellectual capital on sustainability, using cross-sectional data. A total of 800 manufacturing firms listed in SMEDA Pakistan were the population of this study. 510 complete questionnaires were returned, yielding a response rate of 63.75%. The research model developed for this study was analyzed in Partial least squares (PLS). The results show that the two dimensions of GHRM practices (green recruitment and selection, and green rewards) and green intellectual capital (green human capital, green structural capital and green relational capital) have a positive effect on a firm's sustainability. GHRM practices and green intellectual capital have a positive role in this model. Practitioners, scholars and academics all may take benefits from the findings of this study.

Song, Yu and Xu (2020) examined a conceptual model that incorporates the effects of green human capital and management environment concern. Data were collected from 143 firms in China, and the regression analysis and bootstrapping test were used to assess the hypothesis. Our findings indicate that GHRM can positively influence green innovation, and green human capital mediated the link between GHRM and green innovation. In addition, management environment concern moderates the effect of GHRM on green human capital. The results further explore that the indirect effect of GHRM on green innovation through green human capital is significant for the firms with a high management environment concern, but not for this relationship with a low management environment concern.

Bashirun, & Noranee, (2020) carried out a study on influence of Environmental Knowledge and Attitude on Employee Green Behaviour. Environmental issues often get global attention due to increasing environmental damages as seen in global warming, environmental degradation and ozone depletion. By encouraging pro- environmental or green behaviour at workplace, it can encourage the employees to be more responsible in reducing environmental problems. Thus, the issue of employee green behaviour (EGB) has been a topic of interest among scholars in management. The aim of this study was to examine the relationship between employee environmental knowledge and environmental attitude towards employee green behaviour at workplace. The data comprised responses from 108 employees that indicated a moderate level of green practices at work, the study made use of regression model. The study found that there is no relationship exists between environmental knowledge (EK) and environmental attitude (EA) on employee green behaviour (EGB).

The Relationship Between Video-based Interview of the Applicants and Quality Service

Sana & Auranzeb (2016) carried out a study on effects of Green Human Resources Management on Firm Performance: An Empirical Study on Pakistani Firms. The present study aims to investigate the impact of Green Human Resource like green recruitment, green training and development and green learning on the Firm Performance in Pakistan. Responses are gathered from 376 Pakistani firms. The HR Managers provided the information regarding green HRM in their firms. All the responses were collected on five point likert scale using a close ended questionnaire. The data was analyzed using SPSS. Multiple regression analysis is applied to test the effect of green HRM variables; green recruitment, green training and development and green learning on firm performance. The result indicates that all variables significantly affect the performance of the firm. The results are very useful for HR department and top management to develop their policies of green HRM. Future research can be conducted on other functions of HRM and its relation with employees and firm performance.

Kelvin & Kinemo (2018) conducted a study on the Role of Green Recruitment and Selection on Performance of Processing Industries in Tanzania: A Case of Tanzania Tobacco Processors Limited (TTPL). The study investigated the role of green recruitment and selection on performance of processing industries in Tanzania by using Tanzania Tobacco Processors Limited (TTPL) as a case study. The study sought to specifically assess the application of green recruitment and selection at TTPL, determining whether green recruitment and selection attract more and better job candidates, and establishing the relationship between green recruitment and selection and organizational performance. It was found that green recruitment and selection practices are in place and they contribute in attracting more qualified job candidates. The study also found a linear relationship between green recruitment and selection and performance.

Shahab, (2019) conducted a Study on the Impact of Human Resource Cost Reduction Strategies on the Employee Performance in the Semi Government Organizations in Abu-Dhabi, UAE. This research aimed at three research questions directed the investigation concerning level of impact of cost cutting strategies on the employee performance. Hence, the researcher administered 120 randomly selected mid managers and superintendents from a randomly semi government organization in UAE. The findings from the multiple regression implied that the downsizing as a cost reduction strategy has significant negative effect in employee performance; while the strategies like outsourcing, talent management and process management has positive influence on the employee performance. Thus, the study reveals that not all cost reduction strategies provide negative impact on productivity; unless its unscientific effort; similarly, descriptive statistics results from the ANOVA and t-test revealed that the demographic profile of respondents has no effect on any of the components constituting cost cutting strategies on the employee performance. The study provides implications for the groundwork of HR managers, management, government, academicians and future researchers.

Resti and Lenny (2019) conducted a study on the effect of green recruitment, green training on environmental performance in PT WiraCipta Perkasa using employee green behaviour as mediation variable, Jakarta, Indonesia. The purpose of the study was to analyze the influence Effect of Green Recruitment, Training Green Environmental Performance. The study adopted quantitative research with survey method. A total sample of 100 people, Data analysis techniques in this study using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) using PLS (Partial Least Square) as a software, The result shows that Green Training positive and significant impact indirectly through the Employee Green Behaviour on Environmental Performance. The study concludes that green recruitment, green training and employee green behaviour positive and significant effect on the behaviour of environmental performance. The study recommended that recruitment through an online system needs the process of hiring through the system.

Mohammed (2020) conducted a study on empirical evidence on impact of green human resource management practices and organization's sustainability in Saudi Arabia. The purpose of the study was to investigate the impact of green human resource management practices (GHRMP) on an organization's sustainability, which are intertwined and fragmented in a resource-based view discipline. For this purpose, a survey was conducted in healthcare services and manufacturing organizations in Saudi Arabia. Non probability chain sampling was used a total 136 completed questionnaires were used in the analysis. Descriptive and inferential statistics such as mean, standard deviation, Cronbach alpha confirmatory factor analysis CFA, measurement and structural models were also used. The study shows that GHRMP have a positive and significant impact upon sustainability. The study concludes that Green human

resource management and sustainable performance is a relatively new concept and organizations realized its importance and this is why firms are taking a keen interest to implement GHRMPs in organizations.

Gap in Empirical Review

Some studies done were carried outside green recruitment management practices and Performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state and did not focus to best of my knowledge on the online application of candidates and output and Video-based interview of the applicants and reduced expenses of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state. Most of the studies reviewed analyzed their data through Multiple regression analysis, Path analysis method, Simple random sampling technique, Research questions, Quantitative research with survey method, Non probability chain sampling, Partial least squares (PLS), Regression analysis and bootstrapping test and Descriptive survey while the present study made use of Pearson correlation (r) to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling the research gap by evaluating the green recruitment management practices and Performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state.

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed descriptive survey design. The survey research is one in which a group of people or items is studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire group. It is economical.

Source of Data

Data are classified as either primary or secondary data. The classification was based on the two possible sources: primary source and secondary source.

Primary Source

The primary source was questionnaire. A primary source is the one which the data is collected directly (usually first-hand) by the researcher.

Sources of Secondary Data

Secondary data source was the one which the data is obtained from published materials, internet websites, reports, dailies, text books and so on from the library of the institutions understudy. Sources of secondary can be split into two parts internal and external sources.

Area of Study

The areas of the study were five (5) selected food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state, Nigeria. The food and beverage manufacturing firms understudy include: Nigerian Bottling Company Ltd (NBC), Plot 26, Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout; Adietz Foods, 10 Shadrach Avenue, Elelenwo, Port Harcourt; Marto Foods and Integrated Services, No 7 Nnodi Street, Off Ogbuga Road, Port Harcourt, Rivers; RuttsOcean Foods, Plot 125, Oripirisam Nemi Avenue, Off NLNG Road/ Bridge, Amadi-Ama; and UAC Foods PLC, 26, Azikiwe Road, Port Harcourt, Rivers state, Nigeria. These firms were chosen due the number of employees and high ethical standard.

Population of the Study

The population of the study were five (5) selected food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state, with Nine hundred and sixty one (961) selected staff from the firms. To determine the adequate sample size, the study used Freund and William's statistic formula as quoted by (Uzoagulu, 2011). See Table 1 for details.

$$n = \frac{Z^2 N(pq)}{N(e)^2 + Z^2(pq)}$$

Where n = Sample Size

N = The population

p = Probability of success/proportion

q = Probability of failure/proportion
 Z = Standard error of the mean
 e = Limit of tolerable error of 0.05 (or level of significance)
 N = 961
 p = .5
 q = (1 - .5) = .5
 Z = 95 percent = 1.96
 e = 0.05 percent

$$= \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 961 \times .5 \times .5}{961(0.05)^2 + (1.96)^2 \times .5 \times .5}$$

$$\frac{3.8416 \times 961 \times .25}{2.403 + 3.8416 \times .25}$$

$$\frac{922.94}{2.403 + .9604} = \frac{922.94}{3.363} = 274.340 \quad \sim \underline{274}$$

Sample Size Determination

Bowley’s (1937) proportional allocation statistic was utilized to ensure equitable representation of the Universities. Bowley’s (1937) Formula:

$$N_h = \frac{n \times N_h}{N}$$

Where n_h = number of questionnaires allocated to each of the organizations

n = Total sample size

N_h = Number of proposed lecturers to be used from the selected organizations

N = Population size.

Table 1: Questionnaire Allocation to Each Organization

	<i>Name of the Organization</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Calculation</i>	<i>Sample</i>
1.	RuttsOcean Foods,	113	$\frac{113 \times 274}{961}$	32
2.	Adietz Foods,	103	$\frac{103 \times 274}{961}$	29
3.	Marto Foods and Integrated Services	150	$\frac{150 \times 274}{961}$	44
4.	UAC Foods PLC,	359	$\frac{359 \times 274}{961}$	102
5.	Nigerian Bottling Company Ltd	236	$\frac{236 \times 274}{961}$	67
	Total	961		274

Source: Author’s field work 2023

Sampling Technique

The stratified random sampling with a random start was adopted so as to give every unit of the population under study equal opportunity of being selected into sample. The secondary data were collected from firms, journals, publication, textbooks and the internet. Ten questions (10) in the questionnaire were ranged.

Instrument for Data Collection

The main instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire. Copies of the questionnaire were administered to the academic staff. Ten (10) designed questionnaire was used. The responses generated were used thereafter for data analyses.

Validity of the Instrument

The instrument was given to two experts from the industry and academia to measure face and content validity. To make sure that the research instruments applied in the work are valid, the research ensured that the instrument measure the concept they are supposed to measure.

Reliability of the Research Instrument

This was done by administering 20 copies of the prepared questionnaire to the sample of the study. Cronbah’s Alpha was used in determining the extent of consistency of the reliability.

Table 2: Case Processing Summary

		<i>N</i>	%
<i>Cases</i>	Valid	10	100.0
	Excluded	0	.0
	Total	10	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Table 3: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach’s Alpha	No. of Items
.82	10

Scale reliabilities were calculated using Cronbach’s Alpha; the result obtained was 0.810. This shows that the internal consistency of the scale is good for the purpose of this study because it is greater than 0.87 which was good.

Method of Data Analyses

Data from the questionnaire were analyzed with the aid of SPSS version 23 using simple, percentages and correlation co-efficient. Data from the questionnaire were further analyzed using simple percentages, mean and standard deviation. For the 5-point likert scale questions, the scale and decision rule stated below were used in analyzing the findings.

Scale: Strongly Agree (SA) -5, Agree (A) - 4, Neutral(N) -3, Disagree (D) -2, Strongly Disagree (SD),1

Decision Rule: If Mean \geq 3.0, the respondents agree and If mean \leq 3.0, the respondents disagree. The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise rejects the null hypothesis and Z - test was used to test the hypotheses and analyzed with the aid of SPSS.

Results

Distribution and Returned Questionnaire

The section presents and analyzes the data collected for the study. The presentation and interpretation of data were based on the questionnaire administered to the staff of the food and beverages under study. Table 4, shows the Distribution and Return of the Questionnaire from the Universities.

Table 4: Distribution and Return of the Questionnaire

<i>Firms</i>	<i>Distributed</i>	<i>No Returned</i>	<i>percent</i>	<i>No not Returned</i>	<i>Percent</i>
1. RuttsOcean Foods,	32	28	10	4	2
2. Adietz Foods,	29	25	9	4	2
3. Marto Foods and Integrated Services	44	33	12	11	4
4. UAC Foods PLC,	102	80	29	22	7
5. Nigerian Bottling Company Ltd	67	60	22	7	3
Total	274	226	82	48	18

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Two hundred and seventy four (274) copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents and two hundred and twenty six (226) copies were returned representing eighty two (82%) percent, while forty eight (48) copies of the questionnaire were not returned representing eighteen (18%) percent. That showed a high rate of response.

Data Presentation and Analyses

The Relationship between Online Application of Candidates and Output of Food and Beverage Manufacturing Firms in Rivers State

Table 5: Responses on the Relationship Between Online Application of Candidates and Output of Food and Beverage Manufacturing Firms in Rivers State.

		<i>5 SA</i>	<i>4 A</i>	<i>3 N</i>	<i>2 DA</i>	<i>1 SD</i>	ΣFX	<i>- X</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Decision</i>
1	Finding open position through internet attracts quality talents.	435	356	39	30	22	882	3.90	1.258	Agree
		87	89	13	15	22	226			
		38.5	39.4	5.8	6.6	9.7	100%			
2	Applying online helps compare salaries and enhance market top-notch candidates.	445	324	39	20	25	853	3.95	1.290	Agree
		97	81	13	10	25	226			
		42.9	35.8	5.8	4.4	11.1	100%			
3	Online job applications help streamline the process and get more candidates faster.	420	284	69	46	25	844	3.73	1.347	Agree
		84	71	23	23	25	226			
		37.2	31.4	10.2	10.2	11.1	100%			
4	The employee knows where a person has worked previously.	530	188	87	26	31	862	3.83	1.427	Agree
		106	47	29	13	31	226			
		46.9	20.8	12.8	5.8	13.7	100%			
5	The candidates preview skill levels are noted with online application that is the experience.	555	184	93	24	26	882	3.90	1.369	Agree
		111	46	31	12	26	226			
		49.1	20.4	13.7	5.3	11.5	100%			
	Total Grand mean and standard deviation							3.862	1.3382	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 5, 176 respondents out of 226 representing 77.9 percent agreed that finding open position through internet attracts quality talents with mean score 3.90 and standard deviation of 1.258. Applying online helps compare salaries and enhance market top-notch candidates 178 respondents representing 78.7 percent agreed with mean score of 3.95 and standard deviation of 1.290. Online job applications help streamline the process and get more candidates faster 155 respondents representing 68.6 percent agreed with mean score of 3.73 and standard deviation of 1.347. The employee knows where a person has worked previously 153 respondents representing 67.7 percent agreed with mean score of 3.83 and 1.427. The candidates preview skill levels are noted with online application that is the experience 157 respondents representing 69.5 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.90 and standard deviation 1.369.

The Relationship between Video-based Interview of the Applicants and Quality Service of Food and Beverage Manufacturing Firms in Rivers State

Table 6: Responses on the Relationship between Video-based Interview of the Applicants and Quality Service of Food and Beverage Manufacturing Firms in Rivers State

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	The videos are vital for employee to better not the most pronging candidates.	385	180	165	16	36	782	3.50	1.418	Agree
		77	45	55	13	36	226			
		34.1	19.9	24.3	5.8	15.9	100%			
2	The use of videos allows hiring managers to screen candidates more thoroughly because it shows the employees presentation creativity.	380	300	75	48	26	829	3.67	1.343	Agree
		76	75	25	24	26	226			
		33.6	33.2	11.1	10.6	11.5	100%			
3	Videos help reach more candidates at very low cost	410	244	102	20	39	895	3.61	1.448	Agree
		82	61	34	10	39	226			
		36.3	27.0	15.0	4.4	17.3	100%			
4	The video-based provided instate feedback	460	232	117	16	29	854	3.78	1.355	Agree
		92	58	39	8	29	226			
		40.7	25.7	17.3	3.5	12.8	100%			
5	The use of video reduces the overall number of candidates and increases the number of quality application.	260	232	201	24	37	754	3.34	1.334	Agree
		52	58	67	12	37	226			
		23.0	25.7	29.6	5.3	16.4	100%			
	Total Grand mean and standard deviation							3.58	1.379	
									6	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 6, 122 respondents out of 226 representing 54.0 percent agreed that the videos are vital for employee to better not the most pronging candidates with mean score 3.50 and standard deviation of 1.418. The use of videos allows hiring managers to screen candidates more thoroughly because it shows the employees presentation creativity 151 respondents representing 66.8 percent agreed with mean score of 3.67 and standard deviation of 1.343. Videos help reach more candidates at very low cost 143 respondents representing 63.3 percent agreed with mean score of 3.61 and standard deviation of 1.448. The video-based provided instate feedback 150 respondents representing 66.4 percent agreed with mean score of 3.78 and 1.355. The use of video reduces the overall number of candidates and increases the number of quality application 110 respondents representing 48.7 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.34 and standard deviation 1.334.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: Online Application of Candidates has Relationship with the Output of Food and Beverage Manufacturing Firms in Rivers State.

Table 7: shows the correlation of Online application of candidates has relationship with the output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state

		Correlations				
		Finding open position through internet attracts quality talents.	Applying online helps compare salaries and enhance market top-notch candidates.	Online job applications help streamline the process and get more candidates faster.	The employee knows where a person has worked previously.	The candidates preview skill levels are noted with online application that is the experience.
Finding open position through internet attracts quality talents.	Pearson Correlation	1	.674**	.824**	.517**	.616**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	226	226	226	226	226
Applying online helps compare salaries and enhance market top-notch candidates.	Pearson Correlation	.674**	1	.655**	.775**	.760**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	226	226	226	226	226
Online job applications help streamline the process and get more candidates faster.	Pearson Correlation	.824**	.655**	1	.589**	.716**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	226	226	226	226	226
The employee knows where a person has worked previously.	Pearson Correlation	.517**	.775**	.589**	1	.850**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	226	226	226	226	226
The candidates preview skill levels are noted with online application that is the experience.	Pearson Correlation	.616**	.760**	.716**	.850**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	226	226	226	226	226

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 7 showed the Pearson correlation matrix on online application of candidates and the output showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows .517 < .850. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that online application of candidates had significant positive relationship with the output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state. (r = .517 < .850). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of r = .000 with at alpha level for a two-tailed test (r =.517 < .850, p <.05).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .517 < .850$) was greater than the table value of .000, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that online application of candidates had significant positive relationship with the output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state as reported in the probability value of ($r = .517 < .850, p < .05$).

Hypothesis Two: Video-based Interview of the applicants have Relationship with the Quality Service of Food and Beverage Manufacturing Firms in Rivers State.

Table 8: shows the correlation of Video-based interview of the applicants have relationship with the quality service of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state.

Correlations						
		The videos are vital for employee to better not the most pronging candidates.	The use of videos allows hiring managers to screen candidates more thoroughly because it shows the employees presentation creativity.	Videos help reach more candidates at very low cost	The video-based provided instate feedback	The use of video reduces the overall number of candidates and increases the number of quality application.
The videos are vital for employee to better not the most pronging candidates.	Pearson Correlation	1	.718**	.604**	.706**	.871**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	226	226	226	226	226
The use of videos allows hiring managers to screen candidates more thoroughly because it shows the employees presentation creativity.	Pearson Correlation	.718**	1	.476**	.665**	.772**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	226	226	226	226	226
Videos help reach more candidates at very low cost	Pearson Correlation	.604**	.476**	1	.769**	.524**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	226	226	226	226	226
The video-based provided instate feedback	Pearson Correlation	.706**	.665**	.769**	1	.774**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	226	226	226	226	226
The use of video reduces the overall number of candidates and increases the number of quality application.	Pearson Correlation	.871**	.772**	.524**	.774**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	226	226	226	226	226

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 8 showed the Pearson correlation matrix on video-based interview and the quality service showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows $.476 < .871$.

This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that video-based interview of the applicants had significant positive relationship with the quality service of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state. ($r = .476 < .871$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .476 < .871$, $p < .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .476 < .871$) was greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that video-based interview of the applicants had significant positive relationship with the quality service of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state as reported in the probability value of ($r = .402 < .790$, $p < .05$).

Discussion of Findings

The Relationship between Online Application of Candidates and Output

From the result of hypothesis one, the computed ($r = .517 < .850$) was greater than the table value of $.000$, we concluded that online application of candidates had significant positive relationship with the output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state as reported in the probability value of ($r = .517 < .850$, $p < .05$). In the support of the result, Song, Yu and Xu (2020) examined a conceptual model that incorporates the effects of green human capital and management environment concern. The results explore that the indirect effect of GHRM on green innovation through green human capital is significant for the firms with a high management environment concern, but not for this relationship with a low management environment concern. Bashirun & Noranee (2020) carried out a study on influence of environmental knowledge and attitude on employee green behaviour. The data comprised responses from 108 employees that indicated a moderate level of green practices at work, the study made use of regression model. The study found that there is no relationship exists between environmental knowledge (EK) and environmental attitude (EA) on Employee Green Behaviour (EGB).

The Relationship between Video-based Interview of the Applicants and Quality Service

From the result of hypothesis two, the computed ($r = .476 < .871$) was greater than the table value of $.000$, we concluded that video-based interview of the applicants had significant positive relationship with the quality service of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state as reported in the probability value of ($r = .402 < .790$, $p < .05$). In the support of the result, Resti and Lenny (2019) conducted a study on the effect of green recruitment, green training on environmental performance in PT Wira Cipta Perkasa using employee green behaviour as mediation variable, Jakarta, Indonesia. The result shows that Green Training positive and significant impact indirectly through the employee green behaviour on environmental performance. The study concludes that green recruitment, green training and employee green behaviour positive and significant effect on the behaviour of environmental performance. Mohammed (2020) conducted a study on empirical evidence on impact of green human resource management practices and organization's sustainability in Saudi Arabia. The study shows that GHRMP have a positive and significant impact upon sustainability. The study concludes that Green human resource management and sustainable performance is a relatively new concept and organizations realized its importance and this is why firms are taking a keen interest to implement GHRMPs in organizations.

Summary of Findings

Based on the result the following findings were made

- i. Online application of candidates had a significant positive relationship with the output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state as reported in the probability value of $r(95, n=226), = .517 < .850$, $p < .05$).
- ii. Video-based interviews of the applicants had a significant positive relationship with the quality service of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state as reported in the probability value of $r(95, n=226), = .402 < .790$, $p < .05$).

Conclusion

The study concluded that the online application of candidates and Video-based interviews of the applicants had a significant positive relationship with the output and the quality service of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers State. Green Recruitment helps a company to bring more value-adding workers to the company. To hire people who are qualified for the work, you can't just not recruit any person. In any kind of company, recruitment and selection processes are considered essential, because they aid in finding the most qualified candidates for the jobs. Recruitment and selection are vital operations in human resource management, designed to make the best use of employee strength in order to meet the strategic goals and objectives of the employers and of the organization as a whole.

Recommendations

Based on the findings the following recommendations were proffered

- i. The management of food and beverage manufacturing firms should endeavour to have effective online applications to select the best talents for the success of organizational goals and objectives.
- ii. For organizations to eliminate scheduling complications and delays, reducing the risk of losing candidates to faster-moving companies there is a need for Video interviewing. This will reduce the number of shows, Offer Flexibility for Candidates and Increase Safety.

Contribution to Knowledge

The studies done were carried out outside green recruitment management practices and Performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state and did not focus to the best of my knowledge on the online application of candidates and output and Video-based interview of the applicants and quality service of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state. Most of the studies reviewed analyzed their data through Multiple regression analysis, Path analysis method, Simple random sampling technique, Research questions, Quantitative research with survey method, non-probability chain sampling, Partial least squares (PLS), Regression analysis and bootstrapping test and Descriptive survey while the present study made use of Pearson correlation (r) to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study filled the research gap by evaluating the green recruitment management practices and Performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers state.

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